

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PSYCHOSOMATIC CHANGES IN PATIENTS RECOVERED FROM COVID-19

Lazarova M.,

*Chief assistant professor in the Department of Health Economics,
Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tzekomir Vodenicharov, MD, DSc”, Medical University – Sofia
ORCID ID 0000-0003-2163-8751*

Zlatanova T.,

*Professor in the Department of Health Economics,
Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tzekomir Vodenicharov, MD, DSc”, Medical University – Sofia
ORCID ID 0000-0003-1057-6516*

Zlatanova-Velikova R.

*Professor in the Department of Health Policy and Management,
Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tzekomir Vodenicharov, MD, DSc”, Medical University – Sofia
ORCID ID 0000-0003-0849-7341*

ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic put society through a number of challenges. One of them was that of overcoming the short-term and long-term consequences of the disease. One can learn to live with some of those, while others can cause a reduced quality of life and can necessitate a continuous struggle to overcome them – an intention that will not always come to fruition. The goal of this research is to present some psychosomatic changes that have occurred after coronavirus recovery and to what degree they affect the patient's everyday life. The results show that the COVID-19 pandemic has had serious consequences to our health. The conclusions drawn from this study are related to the need for programme creation and strategy development for physical and mental health change prevention in patients, as well as for additional research related to the disease in order further clarify its consequences.

Keywords: COVID-19, pandemic, post-COVID syndrome, psychosomatic changes.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic put society through a number of challenges. One of them was that of overcoming the short-term and long-term consequences of the disease. One can learn to live with some of those, while others can cause a reduced quality of life and necessitate a continuous struggle to overcome them - a goal that will not always come to fruition.

The behavioural and cognitive disturbances after an acute coronavirus infection can have a serious impact on one's life. COVID-19 patients can experience changes in the way they think, their concentration, speech and memory, and those symptoms can have an influence on their ability to work or even on their keeping up with their daily routines [9].

The coronavirus affects people in different ways. Vulnerable groups, such as the elderly and those with pre-existing health problems, experience a greater degree of risk [10].

The goal of this research is to analyse some of the psychosomatic changes which have arrived in patients recovered from COVID-19 and the impact they have on their daily lives and comfort. The research was carried out in the February-April 2023 period.

To realise this goal the following tasks were accomplished:

1. An analysis of the available literature on the type and presentation of psychosomatic changes in patients recovered from Covid-19.
2. A questionnaire-style survey of the patients' opinion on their physical and mental health self-assessment.

Methodology:

The documentary method (a study of the available documents), the graphic method for visualising the results and the sociological method (questionnaire) were used. The opinions of 51 patients who have recovered from COVID-19 were studied via an anonymous questionnaire distributed among patients by general practitioners.

Results and discussion

In an article by Professor Kosta Kostov [5] it is said that there doesn't exist an established and widely accepted definition for proving "Post COVID-19 condition", which is also called "Long COVID by some", which is why the condition is determined by the symptoms and the time frame. There are three defined terms, which are stages in the course of COVID-19.

- acute COVID-19 -symptoms lasting for up to 4 weeks.
- post acute symptomatic COVID-19 - symptoms lasting between 4 and 12 weeks after the onset of the disease.
- post COVID-19 - symptoms lasting >12 weeks since the onset of the disease, which cannot be explained with another illness and whose duration has not yet been determined [6].

Every second (patient hospitalised with COVID-19) has developed the so-called Post COVID-19 Syndrome, show findings from Chinese research conducted after the first wave of the pandemic. In 76% of the patients, at least one remaining symptom could be observed six months after they were discharged. The most

frequent complaints are fatigue, muscle pain, sleep disturbances, depression, and hair loss. The claim that the patients most affected are predominantly among the elderly and the chronically ill is not true. It is estimated that 10 % to 20 % of the previously infected with COVID-19 suffer long-term consequences, with women aged 20-40 being particularly affected.

A survey conducted in the Charité university hospital in Berlin also reached similar conclusions. There were 42 patients participating and they had an average age of 36 years, and 70 % of them were women. All participants suffered from weakness and severe fatigue lasting for 6 months after they have recovered from COVID-19. Symptoms such as cognitive problems, cephalalgia, muscle pain were also observed.

The British health institute NICE defines Post-COVID as a collection of symptoms that have lasted for more than 12 weeks after the initial infection. According to the cardiologist Mariann Gyöngyösi (from the university clinic in Vienna) the most frequent symptoms are fatigue, malaise, memory issues, shortness of breath, chest pain, but also cardiovascular insufficiency and sleep disturbances.

One in five COVID-19 patients has been diagnosed with a mental illness in the first three months after they tested positive for the virus, shows research conducted in the USA by NIHR Oxford Health Biomedical Research Center and The University of Oxford. The electronic health records of 69 million people in the USA, including 62,000 cases of COVID-19, were analysed and the result show that many of them suffer from anxiety, depression and insomnia." [8]

When it comes to the cardiovascular system there can be a feeling of heaviness in the chest, palpitations and tiredness, as well as a swelling of the lower limbs, which are usually observed in patients whose medical history is indicative of chronic vascular insufficiency.

The most frequent neurological symptoms observed in those who have recovered from COVID-19 are cephalalgia, vertigo, peripheral neuropathies, and sleep disturbances (in older patients). Chronic fatigue syndrome occurs in some patients and it is characterised by a physical indisposition and unease, general weakness not related to physical exertion, insufficient sleep, which makes the patients unsuitable for work.

The continuous isolation related to COVID-19 can also provoke the emergence of long-term changes in the

emotional state related to a feelings of loneliness, hopelessness, physical discomfort, anxiety, exhaustion, and physical burnout. People who have had COVID-19 have a heightened risk of developing residual depression, experiencing fear, uncertainty, and post-traumatic stress and abusing toxic substances [7].

The pulmonary symptoms can include protracted cough and heaviness in the chest, and the duration of these symptoms is different.

Complaints related to cutaneous symptoms like rashes, itchiness and hair loss, as well as to muscle and joint pain and tinnitus, can also be observed in the majority of recovered patients.

Summarised published data tracking patients after COVID-19 recovery indicate that:

- two months after hospital treatment no more than 13 % of the discharged patients were fully asymptomatic,
- around 30 % of the patients had 1 or 2 remaining symptoms,
- over 50 % of them had 3 or more symptoms,
- In total two thirds of the patients still had residual symptoms after the symptomatic period.

The most frequently registered symptoms during and after COVID-19 are shortness of breath and fatigue [1,2,3]. The symptoms of muscle and joint pain, loss of taste and sense of smell were also frequently reported [2,3]. This indicates that in the period after the illness there is only a partial recovery of the symptoms and the health status, and that the portion of patients, who are fully recovered even months after the acute phase of the disease is quite small. According to C Carvalho-Schneider et al. the residual symptoms have significant associations with age, hospitalisation, severity of the disease and the presence of dispnoea at the onset of the disease [3].

Results from the questionnaire survey:

The gender distribution of the respondents was 39 women (76.47 %) and 12 men (23.53 %) aged between 24 and 68 years from the city of Sofia. For all of them the COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in changes to their physical and/or mental health to varying degrees, regardless of how long ago they were sick, or whether the disease took a severe or mild form.

Figure 1. How would you assess your physical condition after COVID-19?

Around one-third of the respondents did not feel particularly well about six months after being sick with Covid-19, reporting muscle tension, joint pain, cramps and nasal congestion. 39.22 % report that their state is satisfactory, which includes having gotten used to the

changes to a degree. As little as one fifth feel excellent, which means that they feel like they did prior to the illness, with no changes to their daily life and comfort. One of the accents of our study is the patients' mental health (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Was there any change in your mental health after COVID-19?

Almost half of the participants (45.1 %) report that they experienced drastic change to their mental health, often related to frequent forgetfulness, sleep disturbances, depressive states, cephalalgia and vertigo. In one fourth the change was insignificant, while 20% cannot

access. As little as 9.8 % of the respondents didn't report any change in your mental health after COVID-19. In most respondents there are remaining COVID-19 symptoms, even a long time after recovering from the illness (74.5 %) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Do you still have at least two symptoms of the disease after the illness has subsided?

Almost three-fourths of the participants report at least 2 coronavirus symptoms remaining after their recovery, which are, in most of them, related to both physical and mental health. This includes joint and muscle pain nasal congestion, as well as vertigo, cephalalgia, sleep disturbances, anxiety and unease. In

15.69 % of the respondents, no symptoms are observed, while 9.8 % cannot give an answer. The belief in the future is of utmost importance even if there are residual symptoms. (Figure 4)

Figure 4. How do you feel about your future health condition?

The results are quite encouraging, as 86.27 % of the respondents have a positive outlook on their future. This, in its own way, helps maintain mental equilibrium, the outlook for problem solving and the emotional condition of the survey respondents. As little as 14 % have a pessimistic outlook or don't think about their future in this regard

CONCLUSION

1. According to the literature, in total 2/3 of the patients still had residual symptoms after having had COVID-19.

2. The most frequently registered symptoms after COVID-19 are dyspnea and fatigue, as well as muscle and joint pain, loss of the senses of taste and smell.

3. Some people have remaining symptoms of long-term anxiety, unexplained unease, sleep disturbances and other problems related to mental health.

4. Physical changes, such as pain, weakness, muscle tension

and vertigo, can be further complicated by the long stretches of isolation, the stress from job loss and financial struggles.

5. It can be observed that 90% of the participants have an optimistic outlook on the future state of their health.

Life during a pandemic is considered to govern the daily lives of people to a high degree. They manage to preserve their predominantly optimistic attitude and keep expecting further developments, believing in their own potential to pull through. The data from the literature review and the questionnaire survey show the need for programme creation and strategy development for physical and mental health change prevention in patients, as well as for additional research related to the disease in order further clarify its consequences.

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